

Spaces Versus Dimensions– 8T

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Abstract:

Following the meaning of the main equation and the primordial series, the author suggest shifting the focus from spatial dimensions to matric and topological spaces, as they are the only factors appearing in the main equation. The lack of significance in dimensions also expressed in the mathematical idea of tensors, and the fact that each observer has unique mixture of spatial dimensions.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The main equation (1) does not have in it any expression of any spatial dimensions, which is a positive indication, as these do not effect underlining laws governing it; these are embedded in the matric tensor. In agreement with modern physical theories that encompass the notion of spatial dimension inside a varying entity called a tensor. The main difference we saw in this equation is between two kinds of spaces, the matric tensor and the flow. According to equation (1.1) we concluded that the Ricci flow is the base space, the matric tensor is the total space.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \leftarrow \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \leftarrow \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \leftarrow \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \quad (1.1)$$

The relationship among between the Ricci flow and the Matric tensor is described by fiber bundle. Define the base space, the Flow, and the total space, The Matric Tensor:

$$\mathcal{R} \rightarrow \text{Base sapce}$$

$$\mathbb{M}_T \rightarrow \text{Total Space}$$

$$\psi: \mathbb{M}_T \rightarrow \mathcal{R} \quad (1.12)$$

$$\psi^{-1}: \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{M}_T \quad (1.13)$$

According to the new framework than the spatial dimensions do not play a significant rule. The questions we can ask rather than how many spatial dimensions are there could be the following – "How many matrix tensor spaces are there?" Since in this framework we have infinite packet of manifolds given by equations (1.14) and (1.15) wrapping each other, the answer could be infinity.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M(1)} \frac{\partial M(1)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M(n)} \frac{\partial M(n)}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.15)$$

What is the distribution of Ricci flow between each two manifolds? How many Ricci Flow spaces are there? If there is a Ricci flow space between each two manifolds wrapping than the Ricci flow spaces are exactly half of the matrix tensor spaces.

The Ricci flow can be a result of two manifolds interacting causing raw energy between the distance separations. Such a framework raises many interesting new questions, what is the distance between each two-matrix tensors spaces? Is it a fixed distance or varying distance? Do each manifold has the same Ricci flow space if all assumed stationary? How many universe packets are there? How does the Flow even looks like? The questions are a result of the main equations that do not have any spatial dimensions in them.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The Coupling Constants Series" In: (2021)